

INTERNET OF THINGS CYBER THREATS AND THEIR MANAGEMENT IN IoT

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Annotation: *As we all know, today all developing regions are widely using digital technologies. Also, in the process of using these digital technologies, the demand for IoT (Internet of Things) technologies is increasing. The increase in this demand increases the threat to the security of resources during the use of IoT technologies. Therefore, ensuring the security of IoT is one of the important tasks of today.*

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Today, as we all know, humanity is moving rapidly in all fields through digital technologies and taking great steps towards development. We can cite a number of digital technologies as examples of developments using these digital capabilities. One of them is the IoT (Internet of Things) network, which is currently used by all Internet users. It's no secret that almost the entire population of the world benefits from these services. This, along with creating a number of conveniences for users in Internet networks, also brings a number of negative consequences, which means that ensuring security in IoT is one of the important tasks of today. IoT security (Internet of things security) is a security system aimed at protecting digital devices and internet networks connected in IoT from negative consequences. Each item has a unique identifier and the ability to automatically transfer data over the network. However, keeping devices connected to the internet exposes them to serious vulnerabilities if they are not properly secured. This leads to the use of a number of security hardware and software tools and devices. Also, IoT security is critical for organizations and businesses that are digitally enabled and growing rapidly, as it encompasses a wide range of techniques, strategies, protocols, and actions aimed at mitigating the growing IoT vulnerabilities of modern businesses.

In general, industries and agencies most vulnerable to IoT security threats include, but are not limited to:

- Retail companies.
- Transportation industry.
- Consumer electronics.
- Utilities and critical infrastructure.
- Health care.
- Education.
- State bodies.
- Financial institutions.
- Energy and utility companies.

Also, modern digital devices and professional security specialists are definitely needed to prevent cyber threats.

IoT devices are used in multiple sectors and industries, including:

- Consumer applications – IoT consumer products include smartphones, smart watches and smart homes, which control everything from air conditioning to door locks, all from a single device.
- Business applications – Businesses use a wide range of IoT devices, including smart security cameras, trackers for vehicles, ships and goods, as well as sensors that capture data about industrial machinery.
- Governmental applications – Governmental IoT applications include devices used to track wildlife, monitor traffic congestion and issue natural disaster alerts.

The number of IoT devices worldwide now numbers in the billions. Their increased presence in our daily lives has led to increased scrutiny of their inherent security issues, which we will be exploring here.

There are a number of sources on the evolution of cyber threats over the years. Ever since the concept of IoT first appeared in the late 1990s, people have warned about the potential dangers of a large number of dangerous devices connected to the internet. This was later revealed by many attacks. It is used to hack into refrigerators and TV monitors and send spam to hackers. Many IoT hackers do not target devices themselves, but instead use IoT devices as access points to a larger network.

IoT security attacks include:

- In 2010, researchers discovered that the Stuxnet virus was used to physically damage Iranian centrifuges, attacks began in 2006, but the main attack occurred in 2009. Often considered one of the earliest examples of an IoT attack, Stuxnet targeted control and data acquisition systems in industrial control systems by using malware to infect instructions sent by programmable logic controllers. Attacks on industrial networks continue, with malware such as CrashOverride-also known as Industroyer-Triton and vpnfilter, targeting vulnerable operating technologies and IIoT systems.

- Researcher at enterprise security firm Proofpoint Inc. in December 2013. discovered the first IoT botnet. According to the researcher, more than 25% of the botnet consisted of devices other than computers, including smart TVs, baby monitors and home appliances.

- In 2015, security researchers Charlie Miller and Chris Valasek wirelessly hacked into a Jeep, changing the radio station in the car's media center, turning on its windshield wipers and air conditioning, and disabling the accelerator. They said they could kill the engine, engage the brakes, and disable the brakes completely. Miller and Valasek were able to tap into the car's network through Uconnect, Chrysler's in-car connectivity system.

- Mirai, one of the largest Botnets to date, first attacked the website of journalist Brian Krebs and the French web host OVH in September 2016; attacks occurred at 630 gigabits per second and 1.1 terabits per second, respectively. The following month, the domain name system service provider Dyn was targeted by the network, making a number of websites, including Amazon, Netflix, Twitter and the New York Times, unavailable for hours. The attacks penetrated the network through consumer IoT devices, including IP cameras and routers. Since then, a number of variants of Mirai have appeared, including Hajime, Hide, Masuta, PureMasuta, Evil, and Okiru.

- In January 2017, the Food and Drug Administration announced that embedded systems in radio-frequency-enabled St. Jude medical implantable cardiac devices, including pacemakers, defibrillators, and resynchronization devices, are vulnerable to security attacks and attacks. warned that it could be

- In July 2020, Trend Micro discovered an IoT Mirai botnet loader adapted to new malware variants that help deliver malicious payloads to large IP boxes. The samples found also exploited recently disclosed or undisclosed vulnerabilities in common IoT devices and software.

- In March 2021, security camera startup Verkada had 150,000 live camera feeds compromised by a group of Swiss hackers. These cameras monitored activities inside schools, prisons, hospitals, and private companies like Tesla.

- At the end of 2022, hackers began exploiting 13 IoT vulnerabilities related to remote code execution. They installed a modified version of the Mirai malware on the compromised devices, giving them unauthorized control over the affected systems.

- In March 2023, Akuvox's smart intercom was found to have a zero-day flaw that allowed remote listening and monitoring.

- Also in March 2023, a buffer overflow vulnerability was discovered in the Trusted Platform Module 2.0 protocol, putting billions of IoT devices at risk.

The sheer volume of Internet of Things devices makes their security a high priority and is crucial for the future wellbeing of the internet ecosystem.

1. For device users, this means abiding by basic security best practices, such as changing default security passwords and blocking unnecessary remote access (e.g., when not required for a device's functionality).

Vendors and device manufacturers, on the other hand, should take a broader approach and invest heavily in securing IoT management tools. Steps that should be taken include:

2. Proactively notifying users about devices running outdated software/OS versions.
3. Enforcing smart password management (e.g., mandatory default password changes).
4. Disabling remote access to a device, unless it's necessary for core functions.
5. Introducing a strict access control policy for APIs.
6. Protecting C&C centers from compromise attempts and DDoS attacks.

Imperva cloud WAF helps IoT manufacturers protect their C&C centers by providing on-edge traffic filtering services that ensure only authorized and authenticated client requests are allowed to reach their APIs.

IoT devices are designed to be centrally-managed devices deployed at the network edge. Their built-in processing power and network connectivity enable efficient, scalable monitoring and management of IoT security infrastructure.

Embedded IoT agents can be designed to connect over the network to a master controller responsible for collecting log information, communicating with cloud-based infrastructure, and sending commands to on-device agents. This enables security to be centrally monitored and managed while minimizing the impacts on resource-constrained IoT devices and embedded security agents.

- Key capabilities of centralized IoT device security management, include:
 - Software updates
 - Policy management
 - Security and asset intelligence
 - Cross-device analytics
 - Event log and telemetry collection

The number of IoT devices being deployed into networks is growing at a phenomenal rate, up to 1 million connected devices each day. While IoT solutions are enabling new and exciting ways to improve efficiency, flexibility, and productivity, they also bring a new risk to the

network. Frequently designed without security, IoT devices have become a new threat vector for bad actors to use when launching attacks.

References

1. J. Trull. Responsible Disclosure: Cyber Security Ethics. CSO Online, 2015. Available at: <https://www.csoonline.com/article/2889357/responsible-disclosure-cyber-security-ethics.html> (Accessed 5.2.2020).
2. L. O'Donnell. 2 Million IoT Devices Vulnerable to Complete Takeover. Threatpost, 2019. Available at: <https://threatpost.com/iot-devices-vulnerable-takeover/144167/> (Accessed 17.2.2020).
3. D. Voolf, S. Boddy, and R. Cohen. Gafgyt Targeting Huawei and Asus Routers and Killing Off Rival IoT Botnets. F5 Labs, 2019. Available at: <https://www.f5.com/labs/articles/threat-intelligence/gafgyt-targeting-huawei-and-asus-routers-and-killing-off-rival-iot-botnets> (Accessed 17.2.2020).
4. T. Spring. The Vulnerability Disclosure Process: Still Broken. Threatpost, 2018. Available at: <https://threatpost.com/the-vulnerability-disclosure-process-still-broken/137180/> (Accessed 5.2.2020).
5. N. Stifter, A. Judmayer, P. Schindler, A. Zamyatin, and E. Weippl. Agreement with Satoshi – On the Formalization of Nakamoto Consensus. Cryptology ePrint Archive, Report 2018/400, 2018.
6. N. Fotiou and G. C. Polyzos. Smart Contracts for the Internet of Things: Opportunities and Challenges. European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC), Ljubljana, Slovenia, June 2018.